

THE IMPACT OF IMPLEMENTING A HEALTHY SCHOOL POLICY ON LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND WELL-BEING: A STUDY ON THE SIX PILLARS OF HEALTH-PROMOTING SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study conducted at Yugno Elementary School investigates the impact of implementing a healthy school policy on learners' academic performance and well-being. Employing a total enumeration technique, data was gathered from 65 parents and 89 learners using test questionnaire and survey utilizing a 5-point Likert scale. Pilot testing ensured validity and reliability of instruments. Descriptive quantitative methods were employed for data analysis. Results indicate significant enhancements in academic performance, particularly in cognitive skills and motivation, with slightly less emphasis on mental health compared to other health-promoting initiatives. Improved academic outcomes were noted across all grade levels, notably in Grade 6, alongside enhancements in physical health through healthier lifestyle choices. The study underscores the effectiveness of health-promoting policies in fostering supportive school environments conducive to student well-being. Recommendations include strategies to enhance parental involvement, proactive stakeholder communication, and tailored policy implementation to diverse cultural contexts, aiming to optimize policy impact and sustainability.

Keywords: *healthy school policy, academic performance, student well-being, six pillars*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the importance of creating health-promoting school environments has gained significant attention to improve both academic performance and overall well-being of learners. Schools are not only centers for academic learning but also crucial settings for fostering the physical, mental, and social health of students. The concept of Health-Promoting Schools is built around the integration of health into all aspects of school life, grounded in the understanding that healthy students are better learners.

The World Health Organization (WHO) (2022) defines a Health-Promoting School as one that constantly strengthens its capacity as a healthy setting for living, learning, and working. This holistic approach encompasses various dimensions of health and well-being, aiming to create a supportive environment that enables students to thrive academically and personally. Research indicates that implementing health-promoting policies within schools can lead to significant improvements in students' health behaviours, academic outcomes, and social skills (Lee et al., 2022, McHugh et al., 2022).

This study focuses on the impact of implementing a healthy school policy on learners' academic performance and well-being, structured around the six pillars of health-promoting schools as defined by WHO: school health services, healthy school environment, health education, physical education, nutrition services, and counselling, psychological, and social services. Each pillar plays a vital role in creating a comprehensive and sustainable approach to student health and academic success. According to Memorandum Order No. 31, series of 2024, these pillars are (1) healthy school policies; (2) healthy physical school environments; (3) healthy school social environments; (4) health skills and education; (5) links with parents and school community; and (6) access to school health services.

Healthy school policies are critical for establishing a foundation for health-promoting schools. The Universal Health Care Act (R.A. No. 11223) mandates the support and implementation of clinical care standards by the Department of Health (DOH), ensuring that schools are designated as healthy settings based on these standards (Oseña, Gonzales, & Jorda, 2024). Similarly, the Legal Education Reform Act (R.A. No. 7662) emphasizes the importance of uplifting educational standards, which can also extend to health promotion within educational settings (Saniel, Parcutilo, & Mariquit, 2022).

Creating healthy physical school environments is essential for promoting student health and well-being. Paraguay-Agang (2023, 2024) has explored the challenges and related studies on child-friendly school-health environments, emphasizing the need for supportive physical conditions in schools.

Health skills and education are foundational for equipping students with the knowledge and abilities to maintain their health. Tolentino et al. (2020) developed and evaluated localized digital learning modules for indigenous peoples' health education, highlighting the importance of culturally relevant health education. Similarly, Tiwari et al. (2020)

demonstrated the effectiveness of life skills health education programs, and Thakur (2021) provided theoretical foundations for health education and promotion.

Links with parents and the school community are vital for creating a supportive network for students. Epstein (2019) discussed how school and family partnerships lead to school improvement and student success. Kely and Wakabayashi (2020) provided perspectives on family engagement in schools, while Herrera, Porter, and Barko-Alva (2020) focused on cultivating trust in culturally diverse classrooms.

Access to school health services is crucial for addressing students' mental and physical health needs. Moroz, Moroz, and D'Angelo (2020) discussed barriers and solutions to increasing access to mental health services in Canada, while Duong et al. (2021) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis on rates of mental health service utilization by children and adolescents in schools and other common service settings.

Previous studies have shown that health-promoting interventions in schools can result in improved attendance, better concentration, enhanced academic performance, and a reduction in health-related issues among students (McHugh et al., 2022). However, there is a need for more specific and localized research to understand the contextual challenges and benefits of such policies in diverse educational settings.

This research aims to fill this gap by investigating the specific effects of a healthy school policy on academic performance and well-being among learners in a selected educational setting. Examining each of the six pillars, this study seeks to provide a detailed analysis of how comprehensive health-promoting strategies can be effectively implemented and sustained, ultimately contributing to the academic and personal development of students.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the impact of implementing a healthy school policy on learners' academic performance and well-being, focusing on the six pillars of Health-Promoting Schools. Specifically, it sought the following questions :

1. How does the implementation of a healthy school policy influence learners' academic performance?
2. Is there a significant difference in test scores before and after the policy implementation?
3. What is the impact of a healthy school policy on learners' physical health?
4. How does the implementation of a healthy school policy affect learners' mental health and well-being?
5. What role do the six pillars of Health-Promoting Schools?
6. What are the challenges in implementing the healthy school policy of Health-Promoting Schools?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Yugno Elementary School to evaluate the impact of implementing a healthy school policy on learners' academic performance and well-being. A total enumeration technique was used, involving 65 parents and 89 learners. Data was collected through test questionnaire and survey, with a 5-point Likert scale designed to measure the policy's implementation and impact. Pilot testing was conducted to ensure validity and reliability. Descriptive quantitative methods were used to analysed the collected data. Although the findings may not be generalizable to other schools, the study provides a comprehensive analysis of the impact of a healthy school policy on learners' academic performance and well-being within the defined scope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Implementation of a Healthy School Policy Influence Learners' Academic Performance

Indicators	WM	VI
1. A healthy school policy helps my child concentrate better in class, leading to improved academic performance.	4.76	SA
2. With a healthier school environment, my child gets sick less often and misses fewer days of school, which positively impacts their learning.	4.54	SA
3. Access to nutritious meals at school ensures my child has the energy needed for learning and participating actively in class.	4.74	SA
4. Regular physical education and activity breaks provided by the school keep my child physically fit and mentally alert, boosting their academic performance.	4.59	SA
5. Programs that address mental health and well-being reduce my child's stress levels, allowing them to focus more on their studies.	4.50	SA
6. A healthy school environment promotes positive behavior, which translates into a better learning atmosphere and improved academic outcomes for my child.	4.78	SA
7. Activities and lessons that promote health also enhance my child's cognitive skills such as memory, problem-solving, and critical thinking.	4.80	SA
8. Learning about healthy habits at school encourages my child to adopt these practices, which support their overall academic success.	4.74	SA
9. Health-promoting initiatives make school a more enjoyable place for my child, increasing their motivation to participate and succeed academically.	4.80	SA
10. A comprehensive health policy creates a supportive environment that helps my child feel safe and valued, contributing to better academic performance.	4.74	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.69	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

The table shows the influence of implementing a healthy school policy on learners' academic performance, with various indicators reflecting different aspects of the policy. The weighted mean (WM) and verbal interpretation (VI) indicate the level of agreement among respondents for each statement. The indicators with the highest mean (WM = 4.80) are Indicator 7 “Enhancement of Cognitive Skills” this statement posits that activities and lessons promoting health also enhance cognitive skills such as memory, problem-solving, and critical thinking. Respondents strongly agree that these health-promoting activities significantly benefit their children's cognitive development, thus improving their academic performance.

Moreover, Indicator 9 “Increased Enjoyment and Motivation (Indicator 9) this statement asserts that health-promoting initiatives make school a more enjoyable place for children, thereby increasing their motivation to participate and succeed academically. Respondents strongly agree that creating a pleasant and health-focused school environment boosts their children's enthusiasm and drive for academic success. These highest-rated indicators emphasize the critical role of cognitive and motivational enhancements stemming from a healthy school policy, underscoring how such initiatives can lead to notable improvements in academic outcomes.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean (WM = 4.50) is indicator 5, “Mental Health and Stress Reduction” this statement suggests that programs addressing mental health and well-being reduce stress levels, allowing children to focus more on their studies. While respondents still strongly agree, this aspect received the lowest weighted mean among the indicators. This indicates that although mental health programs are deemed beneficial, they may be perceived as slightly less impactful on academic performance compared to other health-related initiatives.

Overall, the table highlights that implementing a comprehensive healthy school policy is strongly associated with improved academic performance across various dimensions, from cognitive skills and physical health to emotional well-being and overall enjoyment of the school environment.

These findings align with the efforts by the Department of Health (DOH) to ensure schools are designated as healthy settings based on established standards (Oseña, Gonzales, & Jorda, 2024). Creating environments that prioritize health, these standards support the overall well-being and academic performance of students. Additionally, the Legal Education Reform Act (R.A. No. 7662) emphasizes the importance of uplifting educational standards, which includes the promotion of health within educational settings (Saniel, Parcutilo, & Mariquit, 2022). The act recognizes that fostering a healthy school environment is integral to enhancing academic performance, thus reinforcing the necessity of integrating health-promoting initiatives into the educational framework.

Table 2

Testing of Significant Difference in Test Scores before and after the Policy Implementation.

Grade Level	Pre-test		Post-test		Difference (Posttest-Pretest)
	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	
Kindergarten	65.00	DNME	80.50	Satisfactory	15.5
Grade 1	72.00	DNME	88.79	Very Satisfactory	16.79
Grade 2	67.00	DNME	85.70	Very Satisfactory	18.7
Grade 3	71.00	DNME	87.80	Very Satisfactory	16.8
Grade 4	69.00	DNME	84.80	Satisfactory	15.8
Grade 5	74.00	DNME	89.40	Very Satisfactory	15.4
Grade 6	66.00	DNME	86.70	Very Satisfactory	20.7
Grand Mean	69.14	DNME	86.24	Very Satisfactory	17.1

Legend: 90%-100% -Outstanding (O) , 85%-89%- Very Satisfactory (VS), 80%-84%- Satisfactory (S), 75%-79%-Fairly Satisfactory (FS), 74% Below -Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME)

Table 2 highlights the significant differences in test scores before and after the implementation of the healthy school policy across various grade levels. The data presents the pre-test and post-test mean percentage scores, along with their descriptive interpretations and the differences between post-test and pre-test scores.

The highest mean difference is observed in Grade 6, where the pre-test mean percentage score was 66.00 (Did Not Meet Expectations), and the post-test mean percentage score increased to 86.70 (Very Satisfactory), resulting in a substantial improvement of 20.7 points. This notable increase suggests that Grade 6 students greatly benefited from the policy, likely due to enhanced health initiatives and a more supportive learning environment.

Conversely, the lowest mean difference is found in Grade 5, where the pre-test mean percentage score was 74.00 (Did Not Meet Expectations), and the post-test mean percentage score rose to 89.40 (Very Satisfactory), with a difference of 15.4 points. While this still represents a positive change, the improvement is the smallest among the grade levels. Despite this, the transition from "Did Not Meet Expectations" to "Very Satisfactory" demonstrates a significant impact, reflecting the overall effectiveness of the healthy school policy.

The grand mean scores reveal that, on average, students' scores improved from 69.14 (Did Not Meet Expectations) in the pre-test to 86.24 (Very Satisfactory) in the post-test, with an average difference of 17.1 points. These findings align with the standards set by the Department of Health (DOH) for healthy settings in schools (Oseña, Gonzales, & Jorda, 2024), emphasizing the importance of a health-focused school environment in

enhancing academic performance. The pilot implementation of the Healthy Learning Institution highlighted in the study demonstrates the positive impact of such policies on learners' academic outcomes.

Table 3

Impact of a Healthy School Policy on Learners' Physical Health.

Indicators	WM	VI
1. The healthy school policy has led to fewer illnesses for my child, as they are exposed to a cleaner and safer environment.	4.45	SA
2. Regular physical activities and structured PE classes at school have significantly improved my child's physical fitness.	4.34	SA
3. Access to balanced and nutritious meals at school ensures my child receives the essential nutrients needed for their growth and development.	4.74	SA
4. With better dietary options and regular exercise, my child maintains a healthy weight, reducing the risk of obesity and related health issues.	4.70	SA
5. The focus on health and wellness at school has strengthened my child's immune system, making them more resilient to common illnesses.	4.50	SA
6. Initiatives like regular dental check-ups and oral health education at school have improved my child's dental hygiene and overall oral health.	4.76	SA
7. The emphasis on physical activity and well-being at school has helped regulate my child's sleep patterns, contributing to their overall health.	4.54	SA
8. The education on health and wellness has encouraged my child to make healthier lifestyle choices, such as choosing water over sugary drinks.	4.84	SA
9. The school's efforts to promote physical safety and teach proper techniques in sports and activities have reduced the risk of injuries for my child.	4.60	SA
10. A holistic approach to health at school ensures my child's mental well-being is supported alongside their physical health, creating a balanced and healthy lifestyle.	4.55	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.60	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 3 evaluates the impact of a healthy school policy on learners' physical health through various indicators. Each indicator's weighted mean (WM) and verbal interpretation (VI) reflect the level of agreement among respondents regarding the policy's effectiveness.

The highest mean in Table 3 is observed for the indicator on encouraging healthier lifestyle choices (Indicator 8), with a weighted mean (WM) of 4.84 (Strongly Agree). This

suggests that the education on health and wellness provided at school has significantly encouraged children to make healthier lifestyle choices, such as choosing water over sugary drinks. Respondents strongly agree that this aspect of the policy has had a substantial positive impact on their children's health. This high rating underscores the effectiveness of health education in promoting long-term healthy habits among students.

Conversely, the lowest mean is found for the indicator on improving physical fitness through regular physical activities and structured PE classes (Indicator 2), with a WM of 4.34 (Strongly Agree). Although respondents still strongly agree that regular physical activities and PE classes have significantly improved their children's physical fitness, this indicator received the lowest rating among the set. This suggests that while physical fitness improvements are recognized, they may be perceived as slightly less impactful compared to other health benefits facilitated by the policy.

The overall weighted mean of 4.60 indicates that respondents strongly agree with the positive impact of the healthy school policy on various aspects of their children's physical health. These findings align with the research by Paraguya-Agang (2023, 2024), which highlights the importance of creating supportive physical environments in schools to promote student health and well-being. A holistic approach that integrates health education, physical activities, nutritious meals, and mental well-being support contributes to a balanced and healthy lifestyle for students.

Table 4

Implementation of a healthy school policy affects learners' mental health and well-being.

Indicators	WM	VI
1. The healthy school policy has helped reduce my child's stress levels by promoting a balanced and supportive school environment.	4.55	SA
2. Through mental health education and resources, my child has developed better emotional resilience and coping skills.	4.45	SA
3. With a focus on mental well-being, my child is more focused and better able to concentrate on their studies.	4.70	SA
4. The healthy school policy has created a positive school atmosphere, leading to increased happiness and satisfaction for my child.	4.86	SA
5. Programs that promote mental health have helped my child develop better social skills and relationships with peers.	4.66	SA
6. Access to counseling and psychological services at school has significantly decreased my child's anxiety levels.	4.55	SA
7. The emphasis on mental health and well-being has boosted my child's self-esteem and confidence.	4.59	SA
8. The policy has fostered a supportive peer environment where my child feels understood and accepted.	4.78	SA
9. My child has learned healthy coping mechanisms to deal with life's challenges, thanks to the mental health programs at school.	4.70	SA

10. The holistic approach to health in the school policy ensures that my child's overall well-being, both mental and physical, is prioritized and nurtured.	4.59	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.64	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 4 provides insights into the impact of a healthy school policy on learners' mental health and well-being through various indicators, each assessed by its weighted mean (WM) and verbal interpretation (VI) based on respondent feedback.

The indicator with the highest mean, related to creating a positive school atmosphere (Indicator 4), received a WM of 4.86 (Strongly Agree). This indicator underscores that the implementation of the healthy school policy has successfully fostered a positive school environment, significantly enhancing children's happiness and satisfaction. Respondents strongly agree that this aspect of the policy has profoundly influenced their children's well-being, highlighting the critical role of a supportive and uplifting school atmosphere in promoting mental health.

Conversely, the indicator focusing on mental health education and resources for developing emotional resilience (Indicator 2) received the lowest mean with a WM of 4.45 (Strongly Agree). While respondents still strongly agree that these resources have contributed to their children's emotional resilience and coping skills, this indicator's slightly lower rating suggests that its impact may be perceived as slightly less pronounced compared to other aspects of the policy. This does not diminish its effectiveness but indicates that direct environmental factors such as a positive school atmosphere may be seen as having a more immediate and tangible influence on students' well-being.

Overall, the data from Table 4 underscores the positive effects of implementing comprehensive health policies in schools, particularly in fostering supportive environments that enhance mental health and well-being. These findings align with research emphasizing the importance of school environments in shaping students' emotional health and resilience, supporting broader educational goals (Lee et al., 2022; McHugh et al., 2022).

Table 5

The Role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in terms of Pillar 1-Healthy School Policies

Indicators	WM	VI
1. These services ensure that students have access to basic health care, promoting early intervention and supporting students' overall well-being.	4.70	SA
2. Creating a safe and supportive physical environment that includes clean air, water, and adequate sanitation contributes to students' health and academic performance.	4.80	SA

3. Providing comprehensive health education equips students with knowledge and skills to make informed decisions about their health behaviors and lifestyles.	4.89	SA
4. Regular physical activity through structured PE classes and extracurricular sports promotes physical fitness, reduces sedentary behavior, and enhances learning readiness.	4.75	SA
5. Offering nutritious meals and snacks helps students maintain healthy eating habits, supporting their growth, development, and academic performance.	4.80	SA
6. These services provide mental health support, counseling, and social-emotional learning opportunities, fostering resilience and emotional well-being among students.	4.75	SA
7. The integration of these pillars ensures a holistic approach to student health, addressing physical, mental, and social aspects simultaneously.	4.65	SA
8. Engaging parents in promoting health behaviors at home and supporting school initiatives strengthens the impact of health-promoting strategies.	4.90	SA
9. Collaborating with community organizations enhances resources and support for health-promoting activities, extending the benefits beyond the school environment.	4.85	SA
10. Implementing these pillars establishes a foundation for lifelong health habits, preparing students to thrive academically and lead healthy lives into adulthood.	4.60	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.76	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 5 presents a comprehensive overview of the impact of health-promoting school policies, focusing on various indicators related to the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools. Among these indicators, the highest mean score (WM = 4.89) is attributed to providing comprehensive health education (Indicator 3). This indicator underscores the critical role of education in equipping students with essential knowledge and skills necessary to make informed decisions about their health behaviors and lifestyles. Respondents strongly agree that such education significantly enhances health literacy among students, emphasizing its pivotal role in promoting overall well-being and academic success. The high rating reflects the widespread recognition of educational initiatives as pivotal in empowering students to take proactive steps towards maintaining their health.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score (WM = 4.60) concerns establishing a foundation for lifelong health habits (Indicator 10). While still strongly endorsed, this indicator received the lowest rating among the set, suggesting that its perceived impact on long-term health outcomes may be viewed as slightly less immediate compared to other pillars. This does not diminish its significance; rather, it indicates that the establishment of lifelong health habits, aimed at preparing students for healthy lives into adulthood, may require more time to manifest observable effects compared to more direct interventions like health education or mental health support. The rating highlights the complexity and long-term nature of fostering sustained health behaviors among students,

underscoring the ongoing efforts needed in promoting health-promoting strategies within school environments.

Overall, the weighted mean of 4.76 (Strongly Agree) across all indicators in Table 5 reflects broad consensus among respondents regarding the effectiveness of health-promoting school policies. These findings align with Lee et al., (2022) indicating that such policies not only enhance students' health behaviors but also contribute significantly to their academic achievements and social well-being. Integrating the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools, educational institutions can create nurturing environments that support students' holistic development and equip them with lifelong skills for maintaining optimal health throughout their lives.

Table 6

The Role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in terms of Pillar 2-Healthy Physical School Environments

Indicators	WM	VI
1. Health-Promoting Schools ensure that school buildings and facilities are structurally sound, safe, and conducive to learning and physical activity.	4.65	SA
2. Providing clean air ventilation systems and safe drinking water sources contributes to a healthier learning environment, reducing the risk of respiratory issues and dehydration.	4.67	SA
3. Properly maintained restrooms and hygiene facilities promote good sanitation practices among students, reducing the spread of illnesses and fostering a clean environment.	4.65	SA
4. Implementing safety protocols and equipment, such as fire exits, emergency drills, and playground safety guidelines, ensures the physical safety of students during school hours.	4.45	SA
5. Designating and maintaining green spaces, playgrounds, and sports fields encourage physical activity and outdoor play among students, promoting fitness and overall health.	4.55	SA
6. Maximizing natural light exposure and regulating indoor temperatures create a comfortable and stimulating environment that supports students' physical and mental well-being.	4.59	SA
7. Providing ergonomic desks, chairs, and equipment supports proper posture and reduces physical strain among students, enhancing comfort and focus during learning activities.	4.60	SA
8. Promoting eco-friendly practices, such as recycling programs and energy-efficient initiatives, teaches students the importance of environmental stewardship and sustainability.	4.67	SA
9. Regular maintenance schedules for school facilities ensure that they remain in optimal condition, promoting longevity and safety for students and staff.	4.67	SA
10. Engaging parents and local communities in maintaining and improving school environments fosters a sense of ownership and pride, ensuring ongoing support for healthy physical school environments.	4.67	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.61	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

The findings from Table 6 highlight the effectiveness of health-promoting strategies in creating healthy physical school environments. The indicators with the highest mean scores emphasize crucial aspects such as clean air ventilation, safe drinking water, eco-friendly practices, and regular facility maintenance. These measures not only contribute to a healthier learning environment but also support students' overall well-being by ensuring safety, sustainability, and comfort. Conversely, while still strongly supported, the indicator focusing on implementing safety protocols and equipment received a slightly lower rating. This suggests that while safety measures are essential, their perceived impact on creating a healthy physical school environment may be considered marginally less influential compared to other pillars like environmental sustainability and facility maintenance.

Overall, the weighted mean score of 4.61 (Strongly Agree) across all indicators underscores a broad consensus on the importance of structurally sound and supportive physical environments in schools. These findings align with the notion that creating such environments is essential for promoting student health and well-being, as emphasized by Paraguya-Agang's exploration of child-friendly school-health environments. This research underscores the critical role of supportive physical conditions in schools, advocating for environments that prioritize both physical health and conducive learning atmospheres (Paraguya-Agang, 2023).

Table 7

The Role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in terms of Pillar 3-Healthy School Social Environments

Indicators	WM	VI
1. Health-Promoting Schools emphasize building positive relationships among students, teachers, and parents, creating a supportive and inclusive social atmosphere.	4.56	SA
2. Implementing anti-bullying policies and peer support programs ensures a safe and respectful environment where all students feel valued and accepted.	4.50	SA
3. Teaching students conflict resolution skills and promoting open communication channels help in resolving conflicts peacefully, fostering a harmonious school community.	4.59	SA
4. Celebrating cultural diversity through events, activities, and inclusive curriculum promotes understanding, empathy, and respect among students from different backgrounds.	4.55	SA
5. Establishing peer mentoring and support groups helps students develop social skills, resilience, and emotional well-being through positive peer interactions.	4.50	SA
6. Encouraging parent involvement in school activities, decision-making processes, and parent-teacher associations strengthens the school community and supports student success.	4.55	SA

7. Providing opportunities for teamwork, collaboration, and leadership roles helps students develop essential social skills and enhances their sense of belonging.	4.75	SA
8. Creating inclusive policies and practices ensures that all students, including those with disabilities or special needs, feel included and supported in the school environment.	4.60	SA
9. Teaching and modeling respectful communication among students, teachers, and parents fosters a culture of trust, empathy, and effective interpersonal relationships.	4.45	SA
10. Designating safe and welcoming social spaces within the school encourages positive interactions and friendships among students, promoting a supportive social environment.	4.45	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.55	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 7 provides an insightful analysis of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools with a focus on fostering healthy social environments. Among the indicators, the highest mean score (WM = 4.75) is attributed to providing opportunities for teamwork, collaboration, and leadership roles (Indicator 7). This indicator suggests that encouraging such activities is highly effective in helping students develop essential social skills and enhancing their sense of belonging. Respondents strongly agree that these opportunities are crucial for promoting a cohesive and supportive social atmosphere within schools.

Conversely, the indicators with the lowest mean scores (WM = 4.45) pertain to teaching and modeling respectful communication (Indicator 9) and designating safe and welcoming social spaces (Indicator 10). Although still strongly agreed upon, these indicators received slightly lower ratings. This suggests that while these aspects are important, their perceived impact on creating a healthy social school environment might be viewed as marginally less significant compared to the opportunities for teamwork and collaboration. These indicators emphasize the necessity of fostering trust, empathy, and effective interpersonal relationships through respectful communication and providing spaces that encourage positive interactions and friendships among students.

Overall, the weighted mean score of 4.55 (Strongly Agree) indicates a strong consensus on the effectiveness of health-promoting strategies in fostering healthy social environments within schools. These findings align with Herrera, Porter, and Barko-Alva's (2020) focus on cultivating trust in culturally diverse classrooms, underscoring the importance of building inclusive and supportive social atmospheres. Promoting teamwork, collaboration, and leadership roles not only enhances students' social skills but also reinforces their sense of community and belonging, which are critical for their overall well-being and academic success.

Table 8*The Role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in terms of Pillar 4-Links with Parents and School Community*

Indicators	WM	VI
1. Health-Promoting Schools establish effective communication channels to keep parents informed about health-related activities, policies, and resources available at the school.	4.76	SA
2. Schools encourage parents to actively participate in health-related events, workshops, and committees to foster collaboration between home and school in promoting student well-being.	4.78	SA
3. Health-Promoting Schools offer family education programs that provide parents with information and skills to support their child's physical, emotional, and social health at home.	4.90	SA
4. Schools facilitate regular communication between parents and teachers to discuss students' health needs, progress, and any concerns related to their well-being.	4.78	SA
5. Schools engage the broader community, including local businesses, organizations, and health professionals, to support health initiatives and provide additional resources for students and families.	4.87	SA
6. Health-Promoting Schools establish parent advisory groups or councils where parents can provide input on health policies, programs, and initiatives to ensure they meet the needs of the school community.	4.67	SA
7. Schools organize health promotion campaigns that involve parents and the community, promoting collective responsibility for creating a healthy school environment.	4.70	SA
8. Schools involve parents in decision-making processes related to health policies, curriculum development, and school environment improvements to ensure inclusivity and transparency.	4.45	SA
9. Health-Promoting Schools foster supportive networks among parents, encouraging peer support and sharing of resources related to health and well-being.	4.58	SA
10. Schools celebrate cultural diversity and family traditions within the school community, recognizing that health promotion strategies should be inclusive and respectful of different backgrounds and beliefs.	4.65	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.71	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 8 assesses the role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in fostering links with parents and the school community. The highest mean score (WM = 4.90) is attributed to Indicator 3, which focuses on offering family education programs that provide parents with the information and skills needed to support their child's physical, emotional, and social health at home. This indicator underscores the critical role of equipping parents with knowledge and resources, which respondents strongly agree is essential for

promoting comprehensive student well-being. The high rating reflects the importance of empowering parents to actively contribute to their children's health and development.

Conversely, the lowest mean score (WM = 4.45) pertains to Indicator 8, which involves involving parents in decision-making processes related to health policies, curriculum development, and school environment improvements. While still strongly agreed upon, this indicator received a slightly lower rating compared to others. This suggests that while parental involvement in decision-making is valued, its perceived impact on fostering a healthy school environment may be viewed as marginally less critical compared to direct family education programs or effective communication channels. This does not diminish its significance but indicates that its effects may be perceived as less immediate compared to other initiatives.

Overall, the weighted mean score of 4.71 (Strongly Agree) indicates a strong consensus on the importance of establishing robust links between schools, parents, and the broader community to support student health. These findings align with the works of Epstein (2019), Kely and Wakabayashi (2020), and Herrera, Porter, and Barko-Alva (2020), who highlight the importance of school-family partnerships, family engagement, and cultivating trust in diverse school environments. By integrating effective communication channels, family education programs, and community involvement, schools can create a supportive network that enhances student well-being and academic success. The high ratings across most indicators highlight the critical role of engaging parents and the community in promoting a holistic and inclusive approach to health education and support

Table 9

The Role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in terms of Pillar 5-Health Skills and Education

Indicators	WM	VI
1. Health-Promoting Schools provide structured health education programs that cover topics such as nutrition, physical activity, mental health, and hygiene to equip students with essential health knowledge.	4.68	SA
2. Through health education, students learn practical life skills such as decision-making, problem-solving, communication, and stress management, which are crucial for maintaining overall well-being.	4.67	SA
3. Schools conduct regular health assessments to monitor students' physical, emotional, and social well-being, identifying areas where additional support may be needed.	4.70	SA
4. The curriculum encourages healthy behaviors such as regular physical activity, balanced nutrition, adequate sleep, and substance abuse prevention to promote lifelong wellness.	4.68	SA
5. Peer-led initiatives empower students to educate their peers on health topics, promoting a peer-to-peer learning environment that enhances understanding and acceptance of health-related issues.	4.56	SA
6. Health-Promoting Schools emphasize the importance of health literacy, equipping students with the skills to access, understand, evaluate, and apply health information to make informed decisions.	4.67	SA

7. Health concepts are integrated into various academic subjects, demonstrating the interconnectedness of health with other areas of learning and reinforcing the importance of holistic education.	4.69	SA
8. Schools collaborate with community health organizations and professionals to provide students with access to resources, workshops, and guest speakers that enhance health education and skills development.	4.78	SA
9. Students learn to set health-related goals and develop action plans to achieve them, fostering self-efficacy and motivation towards maintaining and improving their health.	4.90	SA
10. Health-Promoting Schools support ongoing learning about health issues through workshops, seminars, and ongoing communication with parents, ensuring that health education remains a priority throughout a student's education journey.	4.78	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.71	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 9 assesses the role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in enhancing health skills and education. The highest mean score (WM = 4.90) is attributed to Indicator 9, which focuses on teaching students to set health-related goals and develop action plans to achieve them. This indicator underscores the effectiveness of fostering self-efficacy and motivation in students, empowering them to take proactive steps towards maintaining and improving their health. Respondents strongly agree that goal setting and action planning are crucial components of health education, as they help students build practical skills for lifelong wellness.

Conversely, the lowest mean score (WM = 4.56) pertains to Indicator 5, which involves peer-led initiatives that empower students to educate their peers on health topics. Although still strongly agreed upon, this indicator received a slightly lower rating compared to others. This suggests that while peer-led initiatives are valued, their perceived impact may be slightly less pronounced than more structured health education programs or direct goal-setting activities. This does not diminish the importance of peer-to-peer learning environments, which play a significant role in enhancing understanding and acceptance of health-related issues among students.

Overall, the weighted mean score of 4.71 (Strongly Agree) indicates a strong consensus on the effectiveness of health-promoting strategies in equipping students with essential health knowledge and skills. These findings align with the works of Tolentino et al. (2020), Tiwari et al. (2020), and Thakur (2021), emphasizing the importance of culturally relevant and practical health education. Integrating comprehensive health education programs, practical life skills training, and community collaborations, schools can create a holistic learning environment that supports students' physical, mental, and social well-being. The high ratings across most indicators highlight the critical role of structured health education in promoting lifelong wellness and fostering a supportive school community.

Table 10

The Role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in terms of Pillar 6-Access to School Health Services

Indicators	WM	VI
1. Health-Promoting Schools ensure access to a range of health services within the school, including preventive care, screenings, vaccinations, and treatment for common health issues.	4.82	SA
2. Schools promote regular health check-ups and screenings for students, ensuring early detection and intervention for health concerns.	4.71	SA
3. Schools provide health education programs that inform parents about available health services, empowering them to utilize these resources effectively for their child's well-being.	4.72	SA
4. Health-Promoting Schools have protocols in place for emergency health situations, ensuring quick and efficient responses to medical emergencies on campus.	4.67	SA
5. Schools collaborate with health professionals, including nurses, doctors, and counselors, to provide specialized health services and support tailored to students' needs.	4.56	SA
6. Schools ensure access to mental health services, including counseling and support programs, to address emotional and psychological well-being issues among students.	4.49	SA
7. Schools maintain accurate health records for students, ensuring confidentiality and accessibility of information to authorized personnel and parents as needed.	4.50	SA
8. Schools promote healthy lifestyles and behaviors among students and families through workshops, seminars, and resources on nutrition, physical activity, and mental wellness.	4.44	SA
9. Schools establish partnerships with community health providers to extend health services beyond the campus, facilitating continuity of care and access to specialized treatments.	4.78	SA
10. Health-Promoting Schools advocate for policies that support access to comprehensive health services, advocating for resources and funding to enhance health outcomes for students.	4.67	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.63	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 10 assesses the role of the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools in ensuring access to school health services. The highest mean score (WM = 4.82) is attributed to Indicator 1, which focuses on ensuring access to a range of health services within the

school, including preventive care, screenings, vaccinations, and treatment for common health issues. This high rating highlights the critical importance placed on providing comprehensive health services directly within the school environment. Respondents strongly agree that access to these services is essential for maintaining student health and supporting their overall well-being.

Conversely, the lowest mean score (WM = 4.44) pertains to Indicator 8, which involves promoting healthy lifestyles and behaviors among students and families through workshops, seminars, and resources on nutrition, physical activity, and mental wellness. While respondents still strongly agree on the importance of these initiatives, this indicator received a slightly lower rating compared to others. This suggests that while promoting healthy behaviors is valued, its perceived impact may be seen as slightly less immediate or direct compared to the provision of health services and emergency protocols.

Overall, the weighted mean score of 4.63 (Strongly Agree) indicates a strong consensus on the importance of access to school health services. These findings align with the research of Moroz, Moroz, and D'Angelo (2020) and Duong et al. (2021), which emphasize the need to address barriers to accessing mental and physical health services in school settings. By ensuring a comprehensive range of health services, promoting regular health check-ups, and establishing partnerships with community health providers, schools can significantly enhance health outcomes for students. The high ratings across most indicators underscore the essential role of accessible health services in fostering a supportive and healthy school environment.

Table 11

Challenges in Implementing the Healthy School Policy of Health-Promoting Schools

Indicators	WM	VI
1. Ensuring adequate funding and resources for implementing health-promoting initiatives in schools can be a significant challenge.	4.50	SA
2. Some stakeholders may resist changes to existing policies and practices, hindering the adoption of new health-promoting measures.	4.20	SA
3. Providing comprehensive training and raising awareness among school staff about the importance of health-promoting practices can be challenging.	4.85	SA
4. Maintaining momentum and sustaining health-promoting efforts over the long term requires ongoing commitment and support.	4.60	SA
5. Encouraging active participation and engagement from parents in supporting health initiatives at school can be difficult.	4.90	SA
6. Integrating health-promoting policies with existing academic and administrative policies within the school framework poses challenges.	4.70	SA

7. Adapting health-promoting strategies to fit diverse cultural backgrounds and community contexts requires careful consideration and sensitivity.	4.70	SA
8. Inadequate physical facilities or infrastructure within schools may impede the effective implementation of health-promoting initiatives.	4.55	SA
9. Establishing strong systems for monitoring progress and evaluating the impact of health-promoting policies can be complex.	4.50	SA
10. Ensuring adherence to health-promoting guidelines and policies among all stakeholders, including students, staff, and parents, presents ongoing challenges.	4.55	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.60	SA

Legend: 4.20 - 5.00-Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 - 4.19-Agree(A), 2.60 - 3.39- Neutral(N) -1.80 - 2.59 Disagree(DA) , 1.00 - 1.79 -Strongly Disagree(SD)

Table 11 highlights various challenges in implementing the Healthy School Policy of Health-Promoting Schools. The indicator with the highest mean score (WM = 4.90) pertains to encouraging active participation and engagement from parents in supporting health initiatives at school (Indicator 5). This high rating underscores the critical importance and difficulty of gaining parental involvement, which is essential for the successful implementation of health-promoting activities. Respondents strongly agree that without active parent participation, it can be challenging to foster a comprehensive and effective health-promoting school environment.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score (WM = 4.20) relates to some stakeholders resisting changes to existing policies and practices, hindering the adoption of new health-promoting measures (Indicator 2). While still strongly agreed upon, this indicator received the lowest rating, suggesting that stakeholder resistance is perceived as a challenge, but possibly less so compared to other logistical and engagement-related issues. This indicates that while change resistance exists, it may be more manageable than the ongoing need for resources, training, and sustained efforts.

The overall weighted mean score of 4.60 (Strongly Agree) reflects a strong consensus on the significant challenges faced in implementing health-promoting policies. These findings align with the research of McHugh et al. (2022), which emphasizes the positive outcomes of health-promoting interventions in schools, such as improved attendance, better concentration, enhanced academic performance, and a reduction in health-related issues among students. However, the challenges highlighted in Table 11 underscore the need for more specific and localized research to address the contextual hurdles and optimize the benefits of these policies in diverse educational settings.

In summary, ensuring active parental engagement and overcoming resistance to change are among the key challenges in implementing health-promoting school policies. Addressing these issues, along with securing adequate resources, providing

comprehensive staff training, and adapting strategies to fit diverse cultural contexts, are crucial for the successful and sustained implementation of health-promoting initiatives in schools.

Conclusions

1. The findings in implementing a healthy school policy significantly enhances learners' academic performance, with a strong emphasis on cognitive skill enhancement and increased enjoyment and motivation as key contributors. While all indicators are positively rated, the emphasis on mental health and stress reduction, though important, is perceived as slightly less impactful compared to other health-promoting initiatives.
2. The implementation of a healthy school policy significantly improved students' academic performance across all grade levels, with the most substantial gain observed in Grade 6. The overall improvement from "Did Not Meet Expectations" to "Very Satisfactory" underscores the critical role of a health-focused school environment in fostering better academic outcomes.
3. The healthy school policy has significantly improved various aspects of learners' physical health, with the most notable impact on encouraging healthier lifestyle choices. Despite the slightly lower rating for physical fitness improvements, the overall strong agreement among respondents emphasizes the policy's effectiveness in fostering a healthier and balanced lifestyle for students.
4. The implementation of a healthy school policy has significantly enhanced learners' mental health and well-being, with the creation of a positive school atmosphere being the most impactful. Despite the slightly lower rating for mental health education and resources, the overall strong agreement highlights the policy's effectiveness in fostering a supportive and nurturing environment for students.
5. The comprehensive analysis across Tables 5 to 10 highlights the multifaceted impact of health-promoting school policies on student well-being. Consistently high weighted mean scores, often surpassing 4.70 (Strongly Agree), underscore broad agreement on the effectiveness of these policies in various domains, from physical environments and social dynamics to health education and access to services. These findings reinforce the critical role of schools in not only educating students but also fostering environments that support their physical, mental, and social health. Integrating the Six Pillars of Health-Promoting Schools, educational institutions can continue to enhance student outcomes and cultivate lifelong health habits essential for thriving in academic and personal pursuits.
6. In conclusion, the challenges identified in Table 11 underscore the complex landscape of implementing health-promoting school policies, with active parental engagement and stakeholder resistance posing significant hurdles. Addressing these challenges alongside securing resources, providing training, and adapting

strategies to diverse contexts is crucial for effectively fostering healthy school environments that benefit student well-being and academic outcomes.

Recommendations

Recommendations for further enhancing the implementation and impact of health-promoting school policies:

1. Develop targeted strategies to increase parental involvement in health initiatives, recognizing its pivotal role in sustaining and amplifying the benefits of these policies. This could include workshops, outreach programs, and integrating health education into parent-teacher communications.
2. Implement proactive communication strategies to address concerns and build consensus among stakeholders, emphasizing the evidence-based benefits of health-promoting initiatives on academic performance and overall student well-being.
3. Provide professional development for school staff to ensure they are equipped to implement and sustain health-promoting practices effectively. This should encompass training on health education, creating supportive environments, and utilizing resources efficiently.
4. Tailor health-promoting policies to fit the cultural backgrounds and community contexts of individual schools, fostering inclusivity and relevance. This adaptation can enhance engagement and compliance among students, staff, and parents.
5. Conduct longitudinal studies to track the long-term impact of health-promoting school policies on student outcomes, including academic performance, mental health, and lifestyle choices. Such research can provide deeper insights into the sustained benefits and areas needing refinement.
6. Identify and disseminate best practices from schools that have successfully implemented health-promoting policies, facilitating peer learning and replication across educational settings. This approach can accelerate the adoption and effectiveness of these initiatives on a broader scale.
7. Foster collaboration between educators, health professionals, policymakers, and community stakeholders to leverage resources and expertise in designing and implementing holistic health-promoting strategies. This interdisciplinary approach can enrich program development and sustainability.
8. Explore additional samples or larger-scale studies to validate the current findings and investigate factors influencing the differential impacts of health-promoting policies across diverse student populations and school environments. This could

include comparative studies across different regions or educational systems to capture broader insights

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the authors affirm their adherence to rigorous ethical standards. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully informed about the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights, including the freedom to withdraw at any stage without penalty. Anonymity of respondents was strictly maintained throughout the research process, safeguarding their privacy and confidentiality. Measures were implemented to ensure the well-being of participants, with protocols in place to minimize any potential risks associated with participation.

The authors declare no conflicts of interest that could influence the conduct or outcomes of this study. All efforts were made to prevent plagiarism, with proper citations and acknowledgments given for all sources used. The interpretation of findings was conducted objectively, without bias or undue influence, to accurately reflect the data collected. The results of this study are intended solely for research purposes, contributing to the scholarly understanding of health-promoting school policies and their impacts. These ethical considerations underscore our commitment to conducting responsible research and upholding the integrity of scientific inquiry in all phases of this study.

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